

Thiopegan Derivatives: Part XXXVII.

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Some 10:11-thiopegan derivatives as potential antibacterial agents have been synthesised by the condensation of various 2-amino benzylideneamines with 2-chloro-4-substituted -5-nitrothiazoles.

Whereas 4-imino thiopegan derivatives¹ showed encouraging antibacterial activity *in vitro*, the more basic thiopegan derivatives² showed only mild activity against Flexner. Since several compounds containing nitro group, particularly chloro-amphenicol have shown marked antibacterial activity it was considered desirable to synthesise nitro thiopegan³ derivatives III as possible antibacterial agents by the following route:

Previously 2-chloro-4-substituted thiazoles have been condensed with (I) in presence of protonic reagents and in phenol melt by heating at 130--40° for 4-5 hr². In the present study the reaction was completed either by heating (I) and (II) in phenol melt at 130-40° for 8-10 minutes or by refluxing together (I) and (II) in ethanol for 1 hr; the yields by the latter procedure being slightly better. This enhanced reactivity is due to the greatly increased mobility of chlorine at position 2 in the thiazole (II) on account of withdrawal of electrons from position 2 by the nitro group as shown.

1. H. S. Sachdev and N. K. Ralhan, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19C**, 109.
2. H. Singh, A. J. Kaur and K. S. Narang, *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 587.
3. H. S. Suri, G. M. Sharma and K. S. Narang, *ibid*, 1964, **41**, 591.

EXPERIMENTAL

Various 2-chloro-4-substituted-5-nitro thiazoles required for the work were prepared according to the method of Narang *et al*⁴ and 2-amino, 4,5-methylenedioxy-benzylidene-; aniline (I, R=C₆H₅), *p*-chloroaniline (I, R=C₆H₄Cl-*p*) and *p*-methoxy aniline (I, R=C₆H₄.OCH₃-*p*)⁵ were obtained by the condensation of equivalent amounts of 6-amino piperonal with aniline, *p*-chloroaniline and *p*-ansidine respectively.

Synthesis of 2-nitro-(3-p-substituted) phenyl-4-substituted anilino-6:7-methylene-dioxy-10:11-thiopega-2:9-dienes: General Procedure: (a) Two-three drops of conc. hydrochloric acid added to equivalent amounts of 2-amino benzylidene amines and 2-chloro-4-*p*-substituted-5-nitro thiazoles, in phenol (5 ml. for 2.74 g. of I, R=Cl) were heated to 130-40° for 8-10 minutes with stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to the room temperature and basified with sodium carbonate solution. The solid obtained was collected by suction washed with water and crystallised from dioxan (Table I),

TABLE I

Synthesis of 2-Nitro-3, 4-disubstituted 10:11-thiopega-2, 9-diene III.

S. No.	2-Chloro-thiazoles used T	Product formed R	R'	Yield %	m.p. °C	M.F.	Analytical results*	
							Found %	Required %
1.	4(4'-Methylphenyl)-T	Cl	CH ₃	37	218	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	C 58.74 H 3.40 N 11.54	58.53 3.45 11.38
2.	4(4'-chlorophenyl)-T	Cl	Cl	36	231	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	N 10.60	10.91
3.	4(4'-bromo-phenyl)-T	Cl	Br	34	229-30	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ Br Cl N ₄ O ₄ S	N 10.20	10.04
4.	4(4'-methyl-phenyl)-T	H	CH ₃	40	195-96	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	N 11.97	12.22
5.	4(4'-bromo-phenyl)-T	H	Br	36	219	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ Br N ₄ O ₄ S	N 11.10	10.70
6.	4(4'-chloro-phenyl)-T	H	Cl	35	215	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₄ S	N 11.90	11.70
7.	4(4'-chloro-phenyl)-T	OCH ₃	Cl	37	215-16	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₅ S	N 10.60 S 6.67	11.02 6.30
8.	4(4'-bromo-phenyl)-T	OCH ₃	Br	40	209	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ Br N ₄ O ₅ S	N 10.00	10.12
9.	4(4'-methyl-phenyl)-T	OCH ₃	CH ₃	50	194	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅ S	N 11.80	11.47

*Microanalysis by Mr B. N. Anand, Microanalyst, Panjab University, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. T. denotes 5-nitro-thiazole.

(b) Equivalent amounts of 2-amino benzylidene amines and 2-chloro 4-*p*-substituted-5-nitro thiazoles were dissolved in alcohol (50 ml. for 2.47 g. of I, R=Cl) and the solution refluxed on water bath resulting in separation of a reddish solid after half an

4. G. M. Sharma, H. S. Suri and K. S. Narang, *This Journal* (communicated).

5. Beil, Vol. 19 I p. 784.

hour. It was further heated for half an hour more to complete the reaction and the solvent removed under reduced pressure; the solid obtained was treated with sodium carbonate solution, filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from dioxan (Table I); the yields given are by (b) above.

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